

ABOUT THE VOLITIONAL QUALITIES OF A HUMAN AND THE BASES FOR THEIR IDENTIFICATION

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Annotation: The article examines the current state of the problem of developing and using the volitional qualities of an individual. It is shown that existing methods for identifying and classifying volitional qualities contribute little to their practical application. The willpower of an individual is the average strength of his expressions of will, the strength of which is the sum of the effectiveness of the manifestation of individual volitional qualities. A method is proposed for constructing a basic system of human volitional qualities, based on the property of independence.

Key words: basic system, expression of will, volitional quality, volitional effort, identification, independence, willpower.

Introduction. In modern psychology there is no clear position on issues related to will and, specifically, the identification of human volitional qualities. The main reason is that there is no general opinion about the content of volitional qualities. Volitional qualities with the same names proposed by different authors often differ in content, and vice versa - their identical contents are given different names [3, 5].

Classification of volitional qualities, if carried out, is sometimes on different grounds. The purpose of our research is a critical analysis of existing approaches to the substantiation of volitional qualities and the proposal of our own classification of them. The classification is based on the non-overlapping content of the corresponding volitional qualities of concepts, which allows us to solve the problem

of their measurement [1, 2, 4]. This is significant for both scientific research and practical activities. Detection of volitional qualities can be used widely: in military psychology, space psychology, sports psychology, occupational psychology and in other areas of psychological science that are actively developing at the present time [6, 8].

In modern psychology, it is believed that an essential sign of a person's will is the presence of various qualities, called volitional [9, 10, 12]. The absence of these qualities in an individual is considered an indicator of a lack of will. Using the concept of volitional qualities has both positive aspects and disadvantages. D. Yu. Turdimurodov and Ya. M. Abdullaev drew attention to the shortcomings of this feature in [6], highlighting three imperfections among them. Firstly, they are not always related to each other, which means that the presence of one of them in a person does not imply the manifestation of other qualities. Secondly, the practice of cultivating volitional qualities shows that their formation requires other personality characteristics (a sense of self-confidence, an adequate level of aspirations and self-esteem), without which determination, perseverance and other volitional properties are impossible, as well as the presence of appropriate motives and knowledge and human skills. Thirdly, the demonstration of volitional qualities does not always indicate the manifestation of will (this can be manifestations of rage, anger) [11, 13]. Nevertheless, psychology follows the path of isolating and subsequently measuring volitional qualities, since this has a very important practical task - predicting human behavior. By determining an individual's volitional qualities and the level of their development, as well as the content of his personality and the specifics of emerging life circumstances, it is possible with a high degree of probability to predict his behavior in situations requiring the manifestation of will [14, 15].

So, if the task is to predict human behavior, then selection is absolutely necessary. Subject to a strict description of volitional qualities, they can be considered characteristics of a person's will (volitional properties). Let us move on

to the consideration of volitional qualities proposed by various authors in order to identify basic volitional qualities with non-overlapping content.

The author identifies the following volitional qualities:

1. Self-control - the ability to restrain one's own impulsiveness and wait, suppressing ill-considered actions.
2. Initiative - the ability to be active, generate intentions, strive to find and offer others ways to solve problems.
3. Persistence - a steady desire to move towards a distant goal, despite emerging obstacles.
4. Organization - the ability to structure and organize your intentions and actions.
5. Decisiveness - the ability to quickly make a choice in a situation that is significant for the subject, independently make responsible decisions and do what you decide, despite obstacles.
6. Self-control - the ability to maintain the necessary internal state in extreme situations.
7. Self-stimulation - actualization of volitional effort with the help of self-order, self-encouragement.
8. Independence - the ability to act effectively without the support of others.
9. Courage is the ability in unusual situations to realize one's intentions and carry out actions, overcoming fear and even at the risk of life, health or one's own prestige.
10. Patience - the ability to long-term suppress the desire to get out of an unfavorable state, that is, stop working and give yourself rest; refusal of impulsive actions, maintaining reasonable inaction or systematic repetition of actions that do not lead to immediate results.

For the first time, the researcher identifies such a quality as self-stimulation. Let's introduce a remark. Self-stimulation reflects one of the mechanisms of will associated with a change in the "meaning" of an action [15, 16]. Therefore, it is associated with a volitional effort aimed at overcoming obstacles that arise on the way to the goal. For example, to take a decisive action in a situation of internal doubt,

a person can actualize a volitional effort, which will manifest itself in maintaining this action and “relieve” (partly) the tension that is caused by doubt [17]. This may also apply to other actions assessed as persistent, restrained, and courageous. Self-stimulation, that is, the activation of volitional effort, especially at the stage of formation of an individual’s volitional qualities, is often necessary when the habit of acting decisively, restrainedly or boldly has not yet been developed.

Thus, there is no unambiguous solution to the issue related to the identification and coordination of volitional qualities in psychology. The list of strong-willed qualities is extremely wide. Their content in many cases is intertwined or does not correspond to the essence of the expression of will [18]. In this regard, the task of ordering the situation arises on the basis of identifying independent basic elements in the set of volitional qualities. These kinds of volitional qualities could form the basis for evaluating each expression of will. To do this, the authors undertook a study to determine independent volitional qualities.

Conclusions. 1. The number of volitional qualities, the basis for their identification, their content and functional purpose vary depending on the author’s position. The volitional qualities proposed by different authors often overlap in their content, or their identical content is designated by different names. This situation does not contribute to either the further scientific application of this concept or its practical use associated with the metrization of human expressions of will.

2. As a basis for drawing up a basic system of volitional qualities, which opens the way for measuring willpower, it is proposed to use their independence. Seven independent volitional qualities have been identified that comprehensively describe any situation requiring the manifestation of willpower. These include endurance, initiative, perseverance, organization, determination, independence and courage.

References:

1. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2021). Testing volitional qualities for students of high schools of secondary school. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(03), 405-413.

2. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2021). Preschool period: pedagogical aspect of education of will in a child. *Current research journal of pedagogics*, 2(09), 47-51.
3. Alikulovich, M. K., & Yuldashevich, T. D. (2020). Development of physical training skills and formation of willpower qualities in extracurricular activities. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol*, 8(3), 2021.
4. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2023). The role of the learning and game environment in the formation of volitional qualities in physical education lessons. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(4), 38-45.
5. Turdimurodov, D. Y. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2023). Pedagogical methods of sports selection in boxing. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(9), 192-168.
6. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2023). Ways to solution problems of psychological control of preparation of young athletes. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(9), 120-126.
7. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2023). Psychological preparation of student boxers. *Procedia of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 13, 165-169.
8. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2021). Willed qualities of a personality and ways of their formation in sport. *ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science*, 12(104), 689-692.
9. Yuldashevich, D. T. (2021). Formation and education of will in schoolchildren in the process of physical education lesson. *Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal*, 64-74.
10. Yuldashevich, T. D. (2022). Education and development of volitive qualities in schoolchildren by means of physical education. *Academicia Globe*, 3(01), 59-62.
11. Yuldashevich, T. D. (2023). Peculiarities of Volitional Qualities in Physical Education of Schoolchildren. *Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education*, 2(2), 217-220.
12. Yuldoshevich, T. D. (2021). The formation of readiness for skilled tensions in the process of physical education. In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 2124).

13. Yuldashevich, T. D. (2023). Volitional Qualities as a Means of Physical Education of a Personality. *European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630)*, 29, 178-181.
14. Турдимуродов, Д. (2022). Жисмоний тарбия дарси мактаб ўқувчиларида иродавий сифатларни ривожлантирувчи восита сифатида. *Жамият ва инновациялар*, 3(6/S), 74–80.
15. Турдимуродов, Д. Ю. (2022). Формирование у подростков волевых качеств в процессе физического воспитания. *Science and Education*, 3(7), 283-289.
16. Турдимуродов Дилмурад Юлдашевич. (2023). Особенности волевых качеств в физическом воспитании школьников. *Modern scientific research international scientific journal*, 1(2), 105–112.
17. Турдимуродов, Д. Ю. Концептуальные проблемы формирования волевых качеств у школьников младшего возраста.
18. Турдимуродов, Д. Й. (2022). Воспитание и развитие волевых качеств у школьников средствами физического воспитания. *Ijtimoiy fanlarda innovasiya onlayn ilmiy jurnali*, 2(1), 204-207.